

Beat-Flow-Interplay (BFI): Interactive Tools for Responsive Beat-Flow Production

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Abstract

In the production workflow of present-day hip hop, the “beat” is often composed before the “flow,” limiting the music’s responsiveness to the lyrics. This production sequence contradicts centuries-old compositional practices in which music is composed after and in response to a pre-existing text. While beats may be limited in pitch content, they offer diverse timbres emerging from the use of digital sampling. The latter is the foundation for a historical connection between hip hop and the work of Pierre Schaeffer, the founding father of sampling. In the project presented in this paper, we explore this connection and suggest a new method for interactive production of hip hop music in which beat making is responsive to the vocalist’s word choices, and flow improvisation is informed by the beatmaker’s sound choices. Expanding on previous studies, we develop a machine-learning-based performance system intended to be utilized by artists and beatmakers.

1 Introduction

Responsive Beat-Flow Production is an ongoing project funded by the Center for Africana Futures (CAF) and hosted by the Entertainment and Recording Industry Management (ERIM) program at the Texas Southern University (TSU) School of Communication (SOC). In this project, we explore novel interactive production methods for hip hop music, where real-time beat making is responsive to word selection, and flow improvisation is informed by the beatmaker’s sound choices.

During the 2023-2024 academic year, we designed and developed a prototype of the BEAT-FLOW-INTERPLAY (BFI) system, an interactive machine-learning-based, network-supported performance system. We began utilizing this system in the creation of original music with artists, beatmakers, and musicians who are members of the ERIM and music communities of TSU. The system’s development and testing process will continue throughout the current academic year and is anticipated to be completed in Fall 2025.

2 Background

In the production workflow of present-day hip hop, the “beat” (i.e., the music) is often composed before the “flow” (i.e., the lyrics). Hence, the flow is written or freely improvised in response to a precomposed beat, fixed in a non-interactive digital file format. As Adams points out (Adams, 2008), this production sequence contradicts centuries-old vocal music compositional practices in which the music’s role is to deliver the text, i.e., it is composed after and in response to a pre-existing text. The separation between the lyrics and the music in hip hop increases when each is created by a different person at different times and different locations. The composer-lyricist collaboration and the single songwriter (responsible for lyrics and music) are replaced in contemporary hip hop music by virtual relationships in which artists download precomposed beats offered online by producers for monetary compensation and a transfer of copyright ownership.

The beat-flow dichotomy poses a challenge to the musical analysis of hip hop. Standard musical analysis is ineffective when applied to hip hop. Pitch-based analysis of lyrics-music relationships

usually focuses on the composer’s choices of pitch material, i.e., melodies and harmonies. While poetic and musical rhythms may play a role in the analysis, the emphasis is on how the composer’s pitch selections color and support the text. Such causality in music creation influenced by the lyrics cannot be identified when the lyrics are written after the music. In addition, beats are typically based on the repetition of limited harmonic and melodic material. With the absence of substantial pitch material in hip hop, the focus in its analysis has shifted to the lyrics, their semantics, poetic rhythm, and rhythmical alignment with the beat (see Adams, 2008, 2009; Krims, 2000; Mattessich, 2019). Adams suggests a method examining “not how the music supports the text, but how the text [rhythmically] supports the music (Adams, 2008).”

While beats may be limited in pitch content, they offer a variety of sounds, timbres, and colors. The diverse timbral palette of hip hop beats emerged from the use of production technologies, primarily digital sampling. As a central stylistic element of hip hop, the use of sampling has established an unusual historical and stylistic connection between this popular genre and the experimental work of Pierre Schaeffer, who is known as the founding father of sampling. In our 2022 study, we presented a method for analyzing and recomposing hip hop beats that is based on this historical connection (Neuman, 2022). The foundation of this method is Schaefferian sound object theory and the TARTYP Generative Grammars introduced in our previous studies (Neuman, 2013, 2014). The method uses machine learning classifications of beat components based on the Schaefferian sound object typology known as TARTYP. It shows how these classifications and the TARTYP generative grammars can be used to re-compose beats. In the Responsive Beat-Flow Production project, we expand the method from our 2022 study to include the flow, i.e., the lyrics and their vocal performance. With the development of the BFI system, we continue to investigate new applications of the TARTYP for real-time composition and computer improvisation, a topic we began exploring in 2015 with the SIG~ Performance Interface (Neuman, 2015).

Using two supervised neural networks coupled with MFCC audio analyzers, the BFI system analyzes audio input signals from the vocalist and the beatmaker. The vocalist uses the system to contribute to beat making, i.e., to generate, in real time, beat components that are mixed with the beatmaker’s tracks. The beatmaker uses the system to influence the flow performance in real time by invoking, through their sound choices, lyrics displayed on a screen as suggestions for the vocalist. As such, the system enables real-time interaction between the performers and supports a creative exchange that interconnects the two performance mediums. In the following sections, we describe the development process of the BFI system, as well as some of its key components and functionalities.

3 BFI System Development

We chose to develop the BFI system in Max8 and to utilize the Fluid Corpus Manipulation (FluCoMa) toolkit available in this environment (Tremblay et al., 2022). The FluCoMa toolkit encompasses both real-time audio analyzers and machine learning algorithms. In the BFI system, we used a Mel-Frequency Cepstral Coefficients (MFCC) audio descriptor (the `fluid.mfcc~` object) and a Multi-Layer Perceptron Classifier (the `fluid.mlclassifier~` object) (Moore, n.d.). With these tools, we created a neural network that accepts thirteen MFCC values as input and outputs a classification of nine sound categories, i.e., sound-object types.

The BFI system includes two such neural networks: the first is a Flow-to-Beat (F-to-B) network, enabling the hip hop vocalist to be involved in the beat making by contributing beat components to the mix in real time; the second is a Beat-to-Flow (B-to-F) network, allowing the beatmaker to influence the flow improvisation by using sound selections to suggest word choices to the vocalist. The F-to-B network is trained with the Schaefferian sound examples of the nine sound-object types known as the Balanced objects (Schaeffer, 1998(1966))¹. In turn, it associates, in real time, the flow performed by the vocalist with one or more of these sound-object types. The B-to-F network is trained with sound samples of lyrics, i.e., recordings of the vocalist performing selected words. The network uses this analysis to associate sounds generated by the beatmaker with word choices, which are then suggested to the vocalist during the flow improvisation.

¹ The Balanced objects sound examples are part of Pierre Schaeffer’s sound collection released in *Solfe`ge de l’objet sonore* (Schaeffer, 1998(1966)).

According to Schaefferian theory, the nine Balanced sound-object types are the most suitable for music (Chion, 2009); that is, sounds utilized in music production most likely fit into one or more of these Balanced sound-object types. The F-to-B network is trained with 54 samples of Balanced sound objects, six samples for each sound-object type. Using the MFCC audio descriptor, multiple datapoints are extracted from each sound sample. Each datapoint includes thirteen MFCC values. The number of datapoints extracted from each sample varies based on the duration of the sample and its spectral characteristics.

The BFI system incorporates two methods for invoking datapoint extraction. In the first method, datapoints are extracted at a fixed time interval of 50 milliseconds; thus, the longer the sample, the more datapoints are extracted. In the second method, datapoints are extracted by a real-time audio slicer (the `fluid.onsetslice~` object) that calculates extraction points based on changes in multiple metrics of the sample's spectrum, including energy, high-frequency content, spectral flux, phase deviation, and more (Tremblay et al., 2022). Using the real-time audio slicer, datapoint extraction occurs with any changes to one or more of these metrics, thereby more closely reflecting the characteristics of the sound. For example, a piano note created by a single attack and sustained with the pedal will get fewer datapoint extractions than a marimba tremolo sound of the same duration. In the latter, more datapoint extractions are caused by the multiple attacks created by tremolo. That said, the longer the duration of a sound is, the more likely changes in its spectrum will occur. Therefore, like the fixed time interval method, the real-time audio slicer extracts more datapoints from longer sounds.

The use of MFCC audio descriptors and the two methods of datapoint extraction are closely aligned with the definitions of sound-object types specified in the TARTYP, the Schaefferian typology table of sound objects (Chion, 2009). In this table, the leftmost column specifies sound characteristics in the frequency domain (i.e., timbre), while the two upper rows (and marking at the bottom of the table) specify sound characteristics in the time domain. The latter includes references to the duration of the sound (e.g., long, moderate, short, etc.) and the way a sound is articulated and produced (e.g., held sound vs. iterative sound). A definition of a sound-object type denoted in the body of the table is a cross-reference between frequency domain and time domain characteristics (Neuman, 2013). In the F-to-B network, the MFCC audio descriptor provides the datapoints describing the sound's frequency domain. The number of datapoints extracted from a sound, which is determined by its duration and articulation, reflects the sound's time domain.

The architecture of the F-to-B neural network comprises an input layer with thirteen nodes that accept thirteen MFCCs for each datapoint, an output layer with nine nodes labeled as the nine types of Balanced sound objects, and two hidden layers with twelve and ten nodes, respectively. This funnel structure of the network increases the network's accuracy. The analysis of the 54 samples of Balanced sound objects, using the MFCC audio descriptor, has yielded a database of over 2000 datapoints with thirteen MFCC values in each point. Datapoints in this database were labeled with one of the nine labels of Balanced sound-object types. Using this database of labeled datapoints, the network can be trained or fitted to achieve an accuracy of 65-70%. Consequently, the network can listen to input signals and make predictions, i.e., output labels specifying the type of sound object it was listening to. In later versions of the BFI system, we achieved an accuracy of approximately 80% by increasing the number of MFCC input values from 13 to 26. Nonetheless, this neural network is part of a system seeking to enhance a creative process. The successful functioning of the network in this system is measured more by the consistency of its labeling and less by its accuracy. Consistent labeling translates into consistent interaction with the user.

In the BFI system, the F-to-B neural network is used by the vocalist. The network analyzes the audio input from the vocalist's microphone and outputs labels of sound objects. The timing or rhythm of label outputs is determined by a real-time audio slicer (the `fluid.onsetslice~` object) mentioned above. It corresponds to the rhythms performed by the vocalist. As demonstrated in the following section, this label output stream can be mapped to control various beat-making tools such as sample players, virtual instruments, and synthesizers. With the F-to-B neural network acting as an intermediary, the vocalist can use their flow performance to control these tools and create various beat components, including drum patterns, drones, pads, and leads.

We created a communication link between the BFI system in the Max8 environment and an Ableton Live session. Using this communication link, we can synchronize the clocks and transports of these two applications, enabling the matching of tempos, as well as play and stop commands. The label

stream mentioned above is converted to MIDI messages, i.e., a MIDI stream, in Max8. This MIDI stream is transmitted to Ableton Live. The BFI system provides the vocalist with five tools they can activate and manipulate with their voice and lyric choices. These tools are programmed in Max8 and control sounds generated by VST plugins in Ableton Live and external analog synthesizers. With additional programming we have implemented in Max8, the start of loops generated in Max8 can be synchronized with the beginning of bars in Ableton Live, just as with loops created within Ableton Live. The vocalist may choose to activate or deactivate any of these tools at any time throughout the performance. The neural network will respond to the audio input at the time of activation. Since the input signal spectrum is being analyzed, the vocalist can elicit consistent responses from the system by repeating their flow performance.

The Beat-to-Flow (B-to-F) network is used by the beatmaker. To establish an interconnection between the F-to-B network and the B-to-F network, we employed the same architecture for both networks, as well as the same number of training samples and labels. However, in contrast with the F-to-B network that converts the vocalist’s flow performance to beat components, the B-to-F network converts sound generated by the beatmaker to text, i.e., to words, which are displayed on a screen as suggestions to the vocalist. Additionally, this network is trained on a different set of samples.

To create the training samples for the B-to-F network, the vocalist selects nine words from a collection of common rap words (see Chan, 2017; Erome-Utunedi, 2017). The vocalist then records six performance variations of each word, treating each word as a sound-object type and creating a training set of 54 samples. Similar to the previous network, these 54 samples are analyzed using the MFCC audio descriptor, yielding a database of MFCC datapoints labeled with one of the nine words selected by the vocalist. This database of labeled datapoints is used to fit the B-to-F network. Listening to audio input from the beatmaker, the network outputs labels, i.e., words that can be displayed on a screen or mapped to select other words from collections prepared by the artists. Like the vocalist, the beatmaker has the choice of when to activate the network and trigger the display of words on the vocalist’s screen, as well as to use repetition to invoke consistent responses from the system.

4 BFI System Description

In this section, we provide a detailed discussion of the BFI System. We start with an overview of the system. We then focus on the Flow-to-Beat (F-to-B) patcher, one of the system’s main Max8 patchers designed for the vocalist. We describe the patcher's components and functionalities that best explain how the vocalist can utilize it.

4.1 System Overview

Figure 1 shows an overview of the BFI system. It is an interactive performance system designed for real-time responsive hip-hop production. It includes two clock-synchronized sub-systems, each containing a neural network. The Flow-to-Beat (F-to-B) neural network is utilized by hip hop vocalists. It enables the control of virtual instruments and analog synthesizers based on audio input received from the vocalist, and the generation of beat components that are mixed with the beatmaker’s tracks. The Beat-to-Flow (B-to-F) neural network is used by the beatmaker. It displays suggestions for lyrics to the vocalist on a screen based on audio input from the beatmaker. As mentioned above, this system is designed to support a creative exchange that interconnects the two performance mediums.

Figure 2 is a flow diagram illustrating the incorporation of the F-to-B neural network in the BFI system. The F-to-B neural network is trained with sound samples from the Schaefferian sound-object collection. In prediction mode, the network analyzes the audio input from the vocalist’s microphone, allowing the vocalist to control multiple sequencers and synthesizers and generate beat components.

4.2 Flow-to-Beat Max8 Patcher

The F-to-B neural network is programmed in the Max8 environment as a component of the Flow-to-Beat (F-to-B) patcher, which is the patcher used by the vocalist. This patcher includes sections that support analysis and classification, as well as sections that facilitate sound control. The analysis

and classification sections encompass all the components necessary for the neural network to function in both training and prediction modes. The sound control sections feature a range of sequencers that facilitate multi-layer sound generation through links with Ableton Live, various virtual instruments, and external analog synthesizers. Figure 3 shows an overview of the F-to-B patcher. The different sections of the patcher are marked with colored letters. In the Max8 environment, creating sub-patchers, i.e., patcher components hidden in the patcher overview, is a common practice. In the following paragraphs, we discuss visible components and sub-patchers (which are hidden components).

Figure 1: BFI system overview.

Figure 2: F-to-B neural network incorporated in the BFI system.

Figure 3: An overview of the F-to-B patcher.

4.2.1 Analysis and Classification

Sections A and B of the patcher include analysis and classification components. These components are used both in the system's training and prediction modes. In the training mode, the analysis of recorded sound (i.e., sound samples) is stored as datapoints in a dataset used for fitting the neural network. In prediction mode, live sound is analyzed and classified, and then converted into a MIDI stream that controls sound generation.

Section A includes a sample player, a source selection option between the sample player and microphone input, an MFCC audio descriptor, and the datasets and label sets. The sample player is the source selected for training, and the microphone input is selected for prediction.

Figure 4 shows the sub-patcher of an MFCC real-time analyzer audio descriptor outputting datapoints of thirteen MFCC values, using the object `fluid.mfcc~` from the Fluid Corpus Manipulation toolkit (Tremblay et al., 2022).

Figure 4: MFCC audio descriptor.

The datapoints extracted by the MFCC audio descriptor above are labeled and saved as training data. The sub-patcher below (Figure 5) creates these training datasets and label sets. The patcher uses nine labels corresponding to the Balanced sound-object types.

Figure 5: A sub-patcher creating data and label sets.

Section B includes the Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP) classifier neural network, Sound Object to MIDI Converter (SOtoMIDI), and network control interface. The MLP Classifier (Figure 6) is a neural network that receives thirteen MFCC values and outputs nine labels corresponding to the nine Balanced sound-object types. Hence, it has an input layer with thirteen nodes, an output layer with nine nodes, and two hidden layers, one with twelve nodes and the other with ten nodes. The MLP Classifier uses the `fluid.mlpclassifier~` from the Fluid Corpus Manipulation toolkit. In prediction mode, the network's predictions are triggered by changes in the audio input spectrum detected by the `fluid.onsetslice~` object, and silence detected by the `fluid.loudness~` object.

Figure 6: Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP) classifier.

The Sound Object to MIDI (SOtoMIDI) Converter is the sub-patcher shown in Figure 7. This sub-patcher converts the label output stream of the MLP classifier into MIDI notes, which in turn can control virtual instruments and synthesizers. The user can map labels to MIDI notes to fit the musical context in which the system is being used, e.g., a specific tonality or modality.

Figure 7: Sound Object to MIDI converter.

As described above, the analysis and classification sections of the F-to-B patcher incorporate a chain of components that includes the MFCC audio descriptor, the MLP Classifier, and the Sound Object to MIDI (SOtoMIDI) Converter. In the prediction mode, this chain receives an input of a live signal and outputs a MIDI stream. The MFCC audio descriptor analyzes the signal in real time, outputting MFCC values. The MLP Classifier classifies this analysis based on the training data and outputs a stream of sound-object labels. The SOtoMIDI sub-patcher converts the latter into a stream of MIDI notes. While this MIDI stream is created whenever an input signal is received from the microphone, the vocalist chooses when and how to use it to generate beat components.

4.2.2 Sound Control and Generation

Sections C, D, I, J, and K include the sound control components of the F-to-B patcher. These sections provide the vocalist with five sound control tools to generate beat components. These tools include

the Drone Loop, the Direct Synth, the PM 16-step sequencer, the Short Phrase sequencer, and the Live 16-step sequencer. They receive the MIDI stream from the SOTO MIDI Converter, described in the previous section. They use this MIDI stream to create sequences and loops based on choices made by the vocalist. Since the MIDI stream is generated from the mic input signal, the vocalist can use their voice and the timing of their choices to manipulate these sequences and loops. For example, the vocalist can choose to activate one of the tools, timing the activation with a specific word or phrase in their flow, creating a distinct sequence or loop. Furthermore, the vocalist can repeat this process, i.e., timing the reactivation of the same tool with the repetition of the same word or phrase, to recreate a similar sequence.

The five sound control tools mentioned in the previous paragraph do not generate sound. Instead, they output their sequences and loops as composed MIDI, i.e., MIDI notes selected from the MIDI stream, set in rhythmical structures, and combined with MIDI information such as velocity and duration. This composed MIDI data is sent by the patcher, through multiple MIDI busses, to an Ableton Live session that incorporates virtual instruments and analog synthesizers. The latter are the actual sound generators of this system. We have taken these additional steps of linking the F-to-B patcher with an Ableton Live session, virtual instruments, and analog synthesizers to achieve better sound flexibility and quality in this production process. Figure 8 is a flowchart of the F-to-B patcher when used by the vocalist in prediction mode. The figure shows a signal flow starting with an audio signal from the vocalist's mic input, converted into sound-object labels and then into a MIDI stream by the patcher's analysis and classification sections, structured as composed MIDI by the patcher's sound control sections and transmitted to Ableton Live for generating sound into the beat mix.

Figure 8: Signal flow of the F-to-B patcher in prediction mode.

Section C of the F-to-B patcher includes the direct synthesizer and the drone loop, two of the five tools that the vocalist can activate and manipulate with their voice. The direct synthesizer plays MIDI notes received from the SOTO MIDI Converter, set in randomly selected durations without structured repetition or loops. The Drone Loop patcher set up a drone. When activated, the patcher captures one note from the MIDI Stream, transposes it to a low range, assigns a long duration, and loops this note.

Section D includes step recorders for the two 16-step sequencers of the patcher, the PM 16-step sequencer of section I, and the Live 16-step sequencer of section K. The sub-patcher shown in Figure 9 is a PM Seq Recorder that records 16 steps for the PM Sequencer. It receives an activation command in inlet one and the MIDI Stream from the SOTO MIDI Converter in inlet two. When activated, this patcher will record 16 steps (i.e., 16 MIDI notes out of the MIDI stream) triggered by spectrum changes detected by the fluid.onsetslice~ object, such as a series of 16 syllables performed by the vocalist. The recorder must complete the recording of 16 steps before the playback can begin. The sub-patcher LS Seq Recorder, also included in section D, records 16 steps for the Live Sequencer.

Figure 9: PM Seq recorder.

The 16-step sequencer of Section I was designed by Philip Meyer (Meyer, 2022). It was adopted by the author for use in the BFI system. The sequencer receives MIDI note and velocity data recorded by the PM Seq Recorder, as well as a step On/Off matrix. The latter is a list of sixteen 1s and 0s, setting the sequencer’s steps to ON or OFF positions. In a 16-step sequencer, the On/Off matrix creates the rhythmical patterns played by the sequencer.

The Live 16-step sequencer of section K uses the `live.step` object available in the Max8 library. Having two 16-step sequencers in the Flow-To-Beat patcher enriches the polyphony. This sequencer receives a MIDI note list and a velocity list from the LS Seq Recorder of section D. Unlike the PM 16-step sequencer, the Live 16-step sequencer does not use a step On/Off matrix. Instead, the step On/Off is created by interjecting zero velocities into the velocity list.

Section J of the F-to-B patcher includes the Short Phrase Sequencer. This sequencer uses the `seq~` object from the Max8 Library. It loops a short phrase invoked by the vocalist. This is not a step sequencer. The looping tempo is synchronized with the Ableton Live session tempo using the `link.phasor~` object. However, the short phrase is not internally synchronized with a subdivision such as the 16-note subdivision of the step sequencer. The loop’s start is synchronized with the beginning of the bar in Ableton Live using a Synch Start patcher.

The Synch Start sub-patcher, shown in Figure 10, is included in sections I, J, and K with the patcher’s sequencers. This sub-patcher synchronizes the beats and bars of sequences and loops created in the F-to-B patcher with the Ableton Live session linked to this patcher. More specifically, the Synch Start sub-patcher ensures that the cycles of all sequences and loops will always start at the beginning of the Ableton Live bar, regardless of when the user activates them. This sub-patcher receives an activation command in inlet one and the Ableton Live beat and bar count in inlet two. Using the `gate` and `sel` objects, the patcher synchronizes the loop start with beat 1 of the bar. Hence, the user chooses when to activate a sequence, but the actual start of this sequence takes place with beat 1 of the immediately following bar, as is the case in Ableton Live.

Figure 10: Synch Start sub-patcher.

In addition to the components described above, sections F, G, and H of the F-to-B patcher include components that link the patcher with an Ableton Live session and enable clock synchronization,

transporter and tempo link, and start/stop synchronization. These components use objects such as transporter, link.session, and link.phazor~ from the Max8 library. The components in section E load MIDI information to the patcher and enable key commands.

5 Creative Testing Environment

As mentioned in the introduction section of this paper, the Responsive Beat-Flow Production project is funded by the Center for Africana Futures and hosted by the ERIM program at the TSU School of Communication (SOC). The TSU Center for Africana Futures (CAF) supports teaching, research, and creative projects focused on Black Digital Humanities and Black Digital Futures. The CAF Research Fellowships support projects that explore topics from one or more fields within Black studies and digital humanities (CAF, n.d.). Founded in 1927, Texas Southern University is one of the largest historically black universities in the United States. The TSU School of Communication (SOC), celebrating its 50th anniversary this year, is one of the oldest communication programs among HBCUs. It is an interdisciplinary academic school with four undergraduate and two graduate programs. The Entertainment and Recording Industry Management is one of the undergraduate programs offered by the SOC. The ERIM curriculum was recently updated to offer four concentrations in management, audio production, multimedia, and sports entertainment (TSU, n.d.)

The ERIM program attracts established and emerging hip hop artists, DJs, beatmakers, and music creators interested in contemporary popular music, its technical production, and business management. As such, the program and its facilities, which include a tracking studio, an overdubbing studio, and a DAW lab, provide an excellent creative environment for testing the BFI system.

In the continuation project proposal submitted to CAF in December 2024, we requested funding that would enable us to conduct rigorous testing of the BFI system, both in the recording studio and in live performances. We suggested a three-fold testing process, including composing musical material that incorporates the BFI system, recording sessions with artists, beatmakers, and musicians using the BFI system, and live performances utilizing the BFI system. With the recent approval of this request, the testing process will take place during the 2025 Summer and Fall semesters. The BFI system's software updates and detailed operation instructions, as well as video evidence of the system's testing and users' critical evaluations, will be posted at <https://israelneuman.com/BFI.html>.

6. Conclusions

In this paper, we discussed the design and development of the BEAT-FLOW-INTERPLAY (BFI) system as part of the Responsive Beat-Flow Production project. The latter is an ongoing creative project of the TSU Center for Africana Futures. The BFI system is an interactive machine-learning-based, network-supported performance system. It utilizes two supervised neural networks, coupled with MFCC audio descriptors, to analyze audio input signals from the vocalist and the beatmaker. Consequently, the vocalist can use the system to generate and control beat components that are mixed with the beatmaker's tracks. The beatmaker can use the system to influence the flow in real time by invoking, through their sound choices, lyrics that are displayed on the screen as suggestions for the vocalist. The testing of the system, in the recording studio and on stage, is anticipated in 2025.

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